

Digital Traffic Signal Implementation in Japan

Antor Md Ahsan Habib
College of Information Science and Engineering
Ritsumeikan University
Shiga, Japan
is0437if@ed.ritsumei.ac.jp

Abstract— This paper presents a new approach to traffic signal control system with artificial intelligence (AI) called Digital Traffic Signal (DTS). The AI would be used to improve the traffic signal controlling system such as without pedestrians, the signal will always remain green for the drivers. On the other hand, without cars on the street, if there are any pedestrians, the signal would immediately turn green to let the pedestrian cross the street. Besides, those who need special needs for crossing the street such as old persons, pregnant women, disabled or injured persons who may need more time rather than the usual time to cross the intersection, AI would be able to recognize them and treat them differently. An online survey of 9 questions was conducted to investigate people’s attitudes towards the current traffic signal system in Japan and the proposed digital traffic signal system. Besides, an observation experiment has been carried out to emphasis on the necessity of the proposed system (DTS).

Keywords—Traffic Signal, DTS, UTMS, AI in Traffic Controls

I. INTRODUCTION

It is an inherit instinct of human beings to lead a secure life in the most convenient way. It is plausible in the sense that ‘once time is lost, it is lost forever’ which compels us to make the best use of our time. Time and security both are important in our life. Due to some limitation of traffic signals, we are sometimes obligated to wait in traffic without proper reasons which makes us feel frustrated. Based on these situations of traffic, this hypothesis has been developed:

“As a pedestrian with no cars on the road, or as a driver with no pedestrians on the road, the signal would immediately turn green.”

In order to implement the hypothesis of DTS, Artificial Intelligence (AI) would be used to monitor the pedestrians and vehicles to control the traffic signal in an instant way which will ensure safety as well as save our valuable time.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. The Current Traffic System in Japan (UTMS)

The Universal Traffic Management System (UTMS) is one of the most developed traffic management system which has been implemented in Japan. UTMS includes Integrated Traffic Control System (ITCS), Advanced Mobile Information System (AMIS), Mobile Operation Control System (MOCS), Dynamic Route Guidance System (DRGS), Public Transportation Policy System (PTPS) and Environment Protection Management System (EPMS). It controls traffic signals by analyzing traffic data acquired by vehicle detectors and also communicates with the drivers providing the current traffic information constantly. According to the UTMS Society in Japan, traffic signals are controlled based on the analysis of traffic data acquired from a signal point at different moments. Based on the traffic data analysis, a specific control system would have been fixed for that signal point. For example: Let’s suppose, traffic intersections near a university have two or three specific periods when it always remains congested such as university opening and closing time or lunch hour. In these particular times, the signal would have behaved differently rather than its usual non-congested time behavior.

B. Limitation of UTMS

UTMS cannot solve the problem of traffic control if the road becomes congested at random times or unexpected congestion in non-congested times, although it has an alternative option like “pushup button for pedestrian” which

is an analogue systematic way to inform the signal controlling system about the awaiting pedestrians. Besides, it cannot solve several problems for particular situation like: (a) an injured or old person who cannot walk fast would need more time for crossing the road, nevertheless the signal light would sustain the same cycle-length time of signal (b) at the mid night, when there is no vehicle or pedestrian on the road, yet still the red signal is shown which is not expedient for pedestrians or drivers. The proposed DTS with AI would able to

solve all of these mentioned problems. Thus, DTS can play an important role for enhancing the safety facility as well as saving time.

III. EXPERIMENT METHOD

A. Online Survey

There was a nine-question survey on Digital Traffic Signal with AI carried out from 17th May to 6th June, 2018 where 67 people participated. Before sharing the questionnaire with the participants, it was checked by two professors. The questionnaire was edited according to their feedback and the final version was again checked. After that, the survey was shared on Facebook, Line, Twitter, Email as well as private message to the all students of ISSE students and some other Ritsumeikan international student as well as the Japanese people including students of Ritsumeikan University (RU) and Kyoto University, workers of RU faculty. The whole survey was executed in English.

B. Observations

An experiment was conducted near Panasonic West Exit Gate (Kusatsu, Shiga) where the system for crossing the road is similar to the proposed system except they control the traffic with human (security guard) and in DTS, AI would play the same role of security guard for controlling traffic. There is no traffic signal near the exit point of Panasonic, they are managing the traffic signal in an analogue way where security staff are used to stop the vehicle when people/vehicle are coming out or entering into Panasonic. The observational experiment was conducted from 16:35 to 17:00 on 5th July, 2018. The reason for selecting the experiment is in this certain time is that it is the time when workers finish their work of day-shift and come out from Panasonic which is the reason of the road remaining congested on this time. The hypothesis was,

“As a pedestrian with no cars on the road, or as a driver with no pedestrian on the road, the signal would immediately turn green”

The security guard are controlling the traffic in the similar idea that has been proposed in the DTS such as when there is no car, they are blocking the road even if for only one people. The length of time they are blocking the street depends on the condition of pedestrians such as old or young people, total number of pedestrians. It has been investigated how they control the time cycle-length in detail.

IV. RESULTS

A. Result of Online Survey

In question one, participants were asked about their nationality. Fifty-four people responded as

international and the remaining twelve people responded as Japanese.

In question two, participants were asked about their gender and according to their response, there were forty-six males, seventeen females and one person who preferred not to say.

In question three, participants were asked whether they are currently in Japan where fifty people responded in affirmative and twelve people responded negatively.

In question four, participants were asked about how they feel while crossing road with traffic signal. Twenty people responded that they don't feel any difficulty, sixteen people responded that they think the signal time is not enough to cross the road in all time, thirteen people responded that they only feel that the duration of signal time is not enough when it is congested, nine people responded that they don't feel any problem at all and there was one who expressed his own opinion in others option that the signal light is not visible enough in the bright light.

In question five, participants were asked what do they do when there is no the vehicle on street at all, yet still have to wait for the pedestrian signal to cross the road. Twenty-nine people responded that they sometimes break the rules and cross the road meanwhile twelve people responded that they always break traffic rules during this situation. Among the rest, twenty-six people responded that they always traffic rules even in this situation.

5. What do you do when there is no the vehicle on street at all, yet still have to wait for the pedestrian signal to cross the road?
66 responses

Figure 1: Result of Question 5

In question six, participants were asked as a driver what do they do when there are no pedestrians waiting to cross the road, yet still have to wait to drive through the signal. Sixty-two people responded out of sixty-seven people in this question. Forty-four people responded that they always wait and never break the traffic rules. In contrast, six people responded that they always break the rules and there were six people who responded that they sometimes break the rules and move on. Among the rest, six people had no idea as they do not have a driving license.

6. If you are a driver, what do you do when there are no pedestrians waiting to cross the road, yet still have to wait to drive through the signal?
62 responses

Figure 2: Result of Question 6

In question seven, the participants were asked about what they do when they are in the midway of the road and the signal starts to change. Forty-four people said that they run to cross while walking and one people said that he returns to his previous position instead of crossing. Nine people responded that in this regard while driving they just speed up and drive fast and on the other hand, nine people responded that they stopped where they are in this situation while driving.

7. What do you do when you are halfway through crossing the road and the signal changes?
64 responses

Figure 3: Result of Question 7

In question eight, the participants were asked about how would they feel if AI were able to control traffic signals according to how many pedestrians and cars there are on the road? (i.e.; as a pedestrian with no cars on the road, or as a driver with no pedestrian on the road, the signal would immediately turn green). Forty-six people responded in affirmative that it would be great and on the other hand, there were nine people who thought that it is not necessary at all and the current system is perfect for them. There were ten people who expressed that they don't trust AI for safety reasons.

8. How would you feel if AI were able to control traffic signals according to how many pedestrians and cars there are...ignal would immediately turn green)
65 responses

Figure 4: Result of Question 8

In question nine, the participants were asked about how would they feel if the "push-button crossing box" (for pedestrians and by-cycle riders only) becomes obsolete as a result of the proposed new AI digital traffic signal. Forty-five people responded in

affirmative that it would be great and in contrast, there was only one people did not like the idea. There were ten people who had no comments and nine people who thought it is neither good nor bad.

B. Result of Observation

The total number of data when the security guard stopped the vehicles on the street and let their workers cross the road is 35 times (counted number). Here is the result:

- (a) Longest average time that crossing guards allowed pedestrians to cross ≈ 20 seconds
- (b) Pedestrians come in clusters and waves
- (c) Average countable of collected data:

Total Observation Number	Average time each count	Average Number of blocked car on street	Average of crossed pedestrians and vehicles
35	11.43 sec	1.75	2.55 Pedestrian and 0.2 vehicles

Table 1: Result of Observation

V. DISCUSSION

A. Discussion of Online Survey

There are several important facts that have been found out from the result of the survey. Those who took part in the survey were well-aware of the current traffic signal system of Japan and the artificial intelligence (AI). Analyzing everyone's response separately, it has been found that almost all female responders are so positive about the traffic rules such as they do not want to break traffic rules in any regard. Besides, they also do not feel safe about AI. On the other hand, the male responders have been pointed out from their responses that they sometimes break rules and they think that AI should be implemented in order to reduce traffic problems mentioned in the questionnaire. It is visible from the research that people sometimes break rules when they feel it is appropriate to break traffic rules and cross. Still, it can be dangerous which may cause some serious problems. Analyzing each participant's responses specifically, it has been found out that the international people living in Japan are not so strict to traffic rules and they occasionally break rules if the road is empty. On the other hand, most of the Japanese people specially women are very sincere to the traffic rules. They obey traffic rules even if in a situation when there's no vehicle or pedestrian on street. Although for young Japanese male person, it is little contrast to always obey the rules.

B. Discussion of Observation

The pedestrian has been counted as cluster and wave. It has been noticed during experiments when there is only one people to cross or only one cluster of people to cross, the required time for crossing the street is equivalent to the required time for only one people. In contrast, when there is more than one cluster, the more time is required such as the longest average time for crossing the street is 20 seconds whereas the normal average time is 11.43 seconds. Besides, old people needs more time than the normal people or young people.

According to the proposed DTS, AI would do the same things by the way the security staff is controlling traffic in Panasonic West Gate. When there would be more cluster of pedestrian, any old, injured or pregnant women, AI would be able to identify them and increase the cycle-length time of the signal to help them cross the street safe and sound.

VI. LIMITATIONS

A. Limitation of Online Survey

There are two limitation on this survey. First of all, there were 54 international participants among 67 participants. As it has mentioned in the discussion that the international people living in Japan are less careful about traffic rules than Japanese people. If there were 50/50 international and Japanese participant, the results of the survey would have been different. The survey has been executed based on people's opinion which was not possible to justify the accuracy. For example: some participants did not response to all question which indicates that participants may have not answer the questions properly or answered questing without properly understanding, language barrier as the survey was in English which may create some misunderstand to the participants etc.

B. Limitations of Observation

The observation was performed only once at the afternoon of Panasonic west gate at the terminal period of day-shift work. If the observation was investigated in different times of day or different days of week, the data would have been different.

VII. CONCLUSION

DTS would be able to investigate the road condition and control the traffic based on the instant data or situation of road. Simultaneously, it would also be able to recognize the persons who

need special treatment such as old, injured, more than one cluster pedestrians and pregnant woman who need more time than the normal time for crossing the street, the DTS will treat them in the different way.

The number of vehicles is increasing day by day. It has become extremely challenging to cope with the rapidly rising amount of transport by the current traffic management system. Traffic jam is causing the wastage of our valuable time. It is one of the main obstacle in the way of our development which we need to conquer by any means. If we can save time along with ensuring security, the traffic system would be able to be in the revolutionary peak of development which would make our life more comfortable and safer. AI is regarded as the most advance technology and it is the ultimate future of the technology which will imply the betterment in tech world in the swiftest way comparing with the other technology. AI has been successfully implemented in various tech field. So, why not AI in traffic?

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Appendix